

BAMBOO

D2.4 Definition of specifications and data requirements for waste heat recovery analysis

Date of document - 12/2019 (M16)

T2.2: Analysis and characterisation of waste heat streams

Authors: Jaio Manzanedo (IKERLAN); Jorge Arroyo (CIRCE); Yolanda Lara (CIRCE); Cristina Gonzalo (CIRCE); Erika Pierri (TUBS); Aristeidis Nikolopoulos (CERTH); Margaret Edwards (COSMO), Irene Solís (AMIII), Víctor Cuervo (AMIII)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820771. Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

BAMBOO

Technical References

Project Acronym	BAMBOO
Project Title	Boosting new Approaches for flexibility Management By Optimizing process Off-gas and waste use
Project Coordinator	Cristina Gonzalo Tirado Fundación CIRCE cgonzalo@fcirce.es
Project Duration	September 2018 - March 2022

Deliverable No.	D2.4
Dissemination level ¹	PU
Work Package	WP 2 - Characterization and management of the plants' flexibility
Task	T 2.2 - Analysis and characterisation of waste heat streams
Lead beneficiary	P4 (IKERLAN)
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	P1 (CIRCE), P2 (TUBS), P3 (AIT), P5 (CERTH), P7 (N-SIDE), PP11 (RINA), P12 (COSMO), P13 (AMIII), P14 (TÜPRAS), P15 (GM), P16 (UPM)
Due date of deliverable	31 December 2019
Actual submission date	17 December 2019

¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820771. Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

Document history			
V	Date	Beneficiary	Author
0.0	06/09/2019	IKERLAN	Jaio Manzanedo (ToC)
0.1	18/10/2019	IKERLAN	Jaio Manzanedo (ToC review from partners suggestions)
1.0	11/11/2019	CIRCE	Jorge Arroyo (Contributions for AMIII demo-site)
1.1	19/11/2019	TUBS	Erika Pierri (Contributions for UPM demo-site)
1.2	22/11/2019	CERTH	Aristeidis Nikolopoulos (Contributions for GM demo-site)
1.3	02/12/2019	IKERLAN	Jaio Manzanedo (Contributions for TÜPRAS demo-site)
1.4	03/12/2019	IKERLAN	Jaio Manzanedo (Consolidated version for review)
2.0	04/12/2019	CIRCE	Yolanda Lara and Cristina Gonzalo (review of consolidated version)
2.1	05/12/2019	COSMO	Margaret Edwards (review of consolidated version)
2.2	11/12/2019	IKERLAN	Jaio Manzanedo (2 nd draft)
3.0	16/12/2019	CIRCE	Yolanda Lara and Cristina Gonzalo (final review by the project coordinator)

DISCLAIMER OF WARRANTIES

This document has been prepared by BAMBOO project partners as an account of work carried out within the framework of the EC-GA contract no 820771.

Neither Project Coordinator, nor any signatory party of BAMBOO Project Consortium Agreement, nor any person acting on behalf of any of them:

- a. makes any warranty or representation whatsoever, express or implied,
 - i. with respect to the use of any information, apparatus, method, process, or similar item disclosed in this document, including merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose, or
 - ii. that such use does not infringe on or interfere with privately owned rights, including any party's intellectual property, or
 - iii. that this document is suitable to any particular user's circumstance; or
- b. assumes responsibility for any damages or other liability whatsoever (including any consequential damages, even if Project Coordinator or any representative of a signatory party of the BAMBOO Project Consortium Agreement, has been advised of the possibility of such damages) resulting from your selection or use of this document or any information, apparatus, method, process, or similar item disclosed in this document.

Table of content

0	<u>EXECUTIVE SUMMARY</u>	7
1	<u>INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES</u>	8
2	<u>METHODOLOGY/PROCEDURE</u>	9
2.1	AMIII	10
2.1.1	NOTES ABOUT DSS TOOL	10
2.1.2	SPECIFICATIONS FOR WASTE HEAT RECOVERY	10
2.1.3	METHODOLOGY APPROACH: PINCH ANALYSIS	11
2.2	TÜPRAS	11
2.3	GM	12
2.4	UPM	13
3	<u>WASTE STREAMS ANALYSIS</u>	14
3.1	AMIII DEMO-SITE	14
3.1.1	STEEL SHOP	14
3.1.2	HOT STRIP MILL	16
3.1.3	GALVANIZING LINES	17
3.1.4	CONTINUOUS ANNEALING LINE	18
3.1.5	PICKLING LINE	18
3.2	TÜPRAS	20
3.3	GRECIAN MAGNESITE	21
3.4	UPM	22
4	<u>WASTE HEAT RECOVERY ANALYSIS</u>	25
4.1	PINCH ANALYSIS IN AMIII	25
4.1.1	PICKLING LINE BASIS PINCH ANALYSIS	25
4.1.2	HIGH TEMPERATURE HEAT PUMP INTEGRATION	29
4.1.3	CONCLUSIONS	37
4.2	TÜPRAS	37
4.2.1	ORC AND AR WASTE HEAT STREAM INTEGRATION	37
4.2.2	SIZING OF ORC SYSTEM HEX	39
4.2.3	RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS	40

4.3 GRECIAN MAGNESITE	41
4.3.1 THERMODYNAMIC SIMULATIONS	41
4.3.2 CONCLUSIONS	44
4.4 UPM	45
4.4.1 SCENARIO 1	45
4.4.2 SCENARIO 2	46
4.4.3 SCENARIO 3	47
4.4.4 CONCLUSIONS	48
5 REFERENCES	49
ANNEX I. - GLOSSARY	50
ANNEX II. - SUMMARY OF DEMO-SITE DESCRIPTIONS RELATED WITH WASTE HEAT RECOVERY	51

0 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main purpose of this document is to present the analysis done for selected demo-sites in relation with the waste heat recovery approach chosen for each of them. This analysis has been done by considering the implications of the integration of the selected technology (ORC or HTHP) and the impact of the change in process parameters due to this integration.

The main conclusions show that a significant energy saving potential can be achieved by means of those waste heat recovery approaches.

For each demo-site, a general description of their facilities is provided, together with the identification of the boundary conditions to be applied and the relevant processes to be analysed according to the different routes of flexibility management applicable.

1 INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

The main purpose of this document is to present a detailed description of the further analysis done within T2.2 for the demo-sites with the highest waste heat recovery potential as identified in D2.2. The present report is the final document of this task which ends in M16 (December 2019).

The main objective of the task is to study the requirements of the waste heat recovery applications, and for that purpose the most suitable integration scheme between the relevant technology (ORC and HTHP) and the waste heat streams have been analysed. The additional data required for this analysis, which has been necessary beyond the available at the time of writing D2.2, has also been gathered in the context of this T2.2. This report summarizes those activities and the conclusions drawn from them.

The analysis for each demo-site has been done by the teaming of the industrial partner and its associated RTO: AMIII-CIRCE, TÜPRAS-IKERLAN, GM-CERTH and UPM-TUBS. Due to different starting points of and partners involved for each demo-site, the type and depth of analysis has been different for each site. Anyway, a common scheme has been kept as far as possible, and thus in this document, the main technical chapters have been divided in sections for addressing each demo-site's particular approach (beside the common chapters for summary, introduction and objectives, conclusions, references and annexes). Those main chapters address the following points: 1) methodology used for each team, 2) the analysis of the present status of the waste heat stream(s) selected and 3) the analysis of the implementation of the waste heat recovery solution for each demo-site.

2 METHODOLOGY/PROCEDURE

Several procedures have been used to describe and analyze the waste heat streams of the different demo-sites in order to assess their potential for waste heat recovery. As both, the sources and the potential recovery schemes considered in each of the demo-sites are significantly different, the selection of the methodology and tools for their analysis has resulted in such different approaches (as summarized in Table 2-1). In the following sections a more detailed descriptions of these approaches is given.

Table 2-1. Methodology approaches for the demo-sites

Demo site	RTO	What	Methodology /Tool	Target/outcome
AMIII	CIRCE	Selection/analysis of streams.	Pinch analysis	Potential saving from HTHP integration in pickling line.
GM	CERTH	Techno economic assessment of waste heat recovery.	Thermodynamic simulations (ASPEN plus).	Potential electricity production and payback period of an ORC from waste heat stream in kiln 3.
TÜPRAS	IKERLAN	Comparison of HEX system for selected stream cooling with and without heat recovery	e-NTU and HEX sizing	Electricity production from waste heat stream. Electricity savings from present unit consumptions.
UPM	TUBS	Waste-heat streams valorization.	Energy flow analysis (eSankey)	Benefits from waste water heat recovery alternatives (including HTHP integration) for bio-sludge drying process.

2.1 AMIII

2.1.1 NOTES ABOUT DSS TOOL

For AMIII, the use case for the Operational Optimization Module is based in a Heat Pump that will be installed in Avilés plant to reduce the amount of steam used from the network.

The heat pump will consume electrical power, therefore there will be an arbitrage to make between natural gas consumption (for steam production from boilers) or electrical consumption (for steam production from the heat pump). This will be done by the Operational Optimization Module of the BAMBOO DSS tool.

Practically, the steam is currently supplied from the plant steam network and is produced by burning either waste stream gas (COG / BOFG) or natural gas. In the future, only natural gas will be used. However, any kW of waste stream gas that is used to produce steam cannot be used for other purposes, requiring natural gas as a replacement in these other applications. Therefore, for the sake of the model all steam from the network will be considered as being produced using natural gas.

2.1.2 Specifications for waste heat recovery

General description of AMIII demo-sites and processes has already been addressed in D2.2 (*Report on material and energy flow characterisation on plant and relevant process level*). Particular features of the processes related to waste heat recovery are summarized in ANNEX II. Within the scope of BAMBOO project, the technology to be demonstrated in the AMIII facilities comprises a heat pump which will receive waste heat to generate steam, decreasing the amount of fuel used to generate steam or the external steam consumption.

To introduce the heat pump in the Avilés facilities, the requirements of this technology must be fulfilled:

- Firstly, the heat pump needs a heat source of about 90 °C. The best option is the use of hot water. If 90 °C hot water is not available in the facility, these alternatives could be possible:
 - Using a heat source at lower temperature (60 °C) which implies an extra electric consumption and cost as well as a reduction in the efficiency of the equipment.
 - Using the thermal heat provided by combustion fumes to heat water to the recommended temperature.
- Secondly, the heat pump needs a high-quality feed water at 102 °C to produce steam. In the steelmaking process it is unlikely to find water streams at so high temperatures. Hence, an alternative to heat this stream is the use of about 5% of the steam generated by the heat pump to preheat the inlet water.
- Additionally, this feed water needs specific qualities since steam can be used for a wide range of purposes where several quality requirements may apply. Some facilities do not need the same high-quality water in their process than the used within the steam generators, thus a water characterization could be necessary to check its suitability to produce steam. Condensates, demineralized water or osmosis water could be good

candidates, while softener water, although presents a low hardness, should be checked to use it with this purpose.

- Finally, the facility must be a steam consumer. In this way, the steam can be produced and used in the same localization, thus reducing costs and heat losses. Hence, the facility must meet the criteria of the technology: a maximum 5 bara steam consumption pressure. The heat pump can achieve a maximum production of 345 kg/h with 6 compressors if the conditions of the streams are optimal.

In order to fulfill the requirements listed above, a characterization of the streams produced in the different Avilés facilities and the advantages or disadvantages of the use of these streams for flexibility has been investigated. These analyses are detailed in section 4.1.

2.1.3 Methodology approach: Pinch Analysis

The pinch analysis is a proven tool to target and design heat integration solutions [1], as is the case of a heat pump, so it has been the method used to analyze the optimal point where the heat pump can be installed within AMIII facilities.

During the pinch analysis, the energy services (steam, water, hot and cold services) of the plant are identified and compared with the real energy needs of the plant (cooling and heating streams).

The pinch analysis leads to an optimal design of a heat exchangers network, which allows the exchange of energy between the hot and cold streams and thus, minimizes the use of the external services.

The application of the pinch methodology provides a target for minimum energy consumption by analysing the temperature-enthalpy profiles of both, heat availability and heat demand in the processes.

2.2 TÜPRAS

In the case of the petrochemical demo-site, the methodology of pinch analysis is widely used in this sector, but usually during the design of new processes or retrofitting of older ones [2]. As described in D2.2 (*Report on material and energy flow characterisation on plant and relevant process level*) the waste heat stream analysis and the potential for ORC integration in Tüpras Izmir refinery showed that AR cooling process is the most practical waste heat stream to be recovered. Since cooling of this AR stream at present is addressed by air coolers and water coolers, and the cooling limit temperature for this stream is fixed, the tie in connection point where the ORC hot heat exchanger will be placed is quite straightforward and thus, the use of pinch analysis is no worth.

On the other hand, part of the OPEX of the present cooling system of the AR stream comes from the fan operations of the air coolers, plus the pumping power of the cooling water. When that cooling requirement is lowered due to the integration of the ORC, part of this OPEX will be affected by either decreasing (e.g. due to less heat duty of air coolers and thus, lower fan electricity consumption) or increasing (e.g. if higher cooling water flow is required by the ORC condenser than for the present water coolers, and thus, higher pumping power results). Moreover, additional OPEX changes can be expected from maintenance operations that can be affected by the ORC integration (e.g. shorter fan operating hours resulting in lowering maintenance costs). Finally, CAPEX changes can also be foreseen for retrofitting of present cooling equipment if heat

duty for them is decreased by the cooling effect of the ORC. However, cooling capacity should stay at the present levels in case ORC system is down and cooling should be performed by the present scheme.

Based upon the above reasoning, the approach used to evaluate the potential benefits of the ORC integration for AR stream cooling has been to:

- first analyze the present cooling capacity with the aid of HEX analysis methods (ϵ -NTU and sizing tools) to obtain some reference values of HEX size and operating energy consumptions
- second evaluate the required HEX capacity for the ORC system within the AR cooling line (using the same tools as above)
- finally compare the OPEX benefits of the waste heat recovery scenario.

2.3 GM

General description of GM demo-site and processes has already been addressed in D2.2 (*Report on material and energy flow characterisation on plant and relevant process level*). In that report, a potential for waste heat recovery was mentioned for rotary kiln 3, subjected to certain constraints to be observed for the downstream processes, which imposed a limitation for the feasibility of the recovery. Further analysis of the process has loosened those constraints, opening the floor for considering the potential of an ORC to take advantage of that waste heat stream. Figure 2-1 shows the process parameters of this kiln.

Figure 2-1. Rotary Kiln #3 process where flue gases can be used for waste heat recovery

Based upon this, the methodology used for GM demo-site to assess the potential of waste heat recovery is as follows: thermodynamic simulations have been performed in ASPEN plus for a state-of-the-art ORC plant with various working fluids, evaluating the potential electricity production at industrial scale. Moreover, a preliminary techno-economic assessment has been carried out for the economic feasibility of such an investment, contributing to the mitigation of the electricity cost of the plant.

2.4 UPM

Within WP2, an integrated methodology has been developed with the aim of evaluating the energy flexibility potential and assessing the potential for waste heat recovery at the UPM demo-site based in Plattling. Figure 2-2 provides an overview of the methodology.

Figure 2-2: Methodology employed at UPM demo-site

A detailed analysis of energy streams within the paper mill has been carried out. As a first step of the analysis, relevant data have been identified: relevant input flows are fresh water, gas, electricity, compressed air and heat; output flows are waste-water, sludge and waste-heat. The analysis includes the whole paper production plant located in Plattling. According to the boundary conditions, set jointly with UPM, the main focus lays however on the waste-water treatment plant and the sludge drying system.

The identified data have been collected at the UPM demo-site as follows:

- flow rate and temperature of fresh water, waste-water and sludge - on hourly-basis
- gas, power and heat demand - on monthly-basis

Based on the gathered data, a Sankey-diagram has been developed with the aim of visualizing the energy flows at factory level. The Sankey diagram has been created using the e-Sankey software tool¹, linked to an excel input-file, including the gathered data as well as the assumptions and calculations made to create the diagram.

Based on the diagram, as third step of the approach, potential waste-heat streams have been identified. The last step consists in evaluating different options to integrate the heat pump. The target application of the recovered waste-heat was defined within the scope of the project, e.g. the operation of the sludge drying facility to be installed in Plattling.

¹ <https://www.ifu.com/en/e-sankey/>

3 WASTE STREAMS ANALYSIS

Existing selected waste heat streams in each of the demo-sites have been addressed to assess their recovery potential when linked to suitable technologies (ORC and HTHP). Not only the requirements of the technologies have been observed but also the restrictions from the industrial processes to keep the performance in terms of quantity and quality of the products as in their present conditions.

3.1 AMIII DEMO-SITE

The next sections contain a description and characterization of the streams produced in the different Avilés facilities and the advantages or disadvantages of the use of these streams for flexibility.

3.1.1 Steel shop

The steel shop is the facility where the pig iron coming from the blast furnace is transformed into steel adjusting the composition and then is solidified. Within the integrated steel route, steel shop has three steps (Figure 3-1): the BOF converter where the carbon percentage is tuned, the secondary metallurgy (2M) where other components are incorporated and finally the continuous casting where the steel is solidified into long products with constant section.

Figure 3-1. Steel shop main streams

The Avilés steel shop has installed an oxygen converter gas treatment system; this allows recovering the waste heat to produce steam and recover the Basic Oxygen Furnace Gas produced in the process.

The flue gases after the combustion of the CO rich gas produced in the BOF, are used to generate steam and exit the boiler at a temperature of around 900 °C. This mixture composes the BOFG stream and can be potentially used as waste heat stream since its temperature needs to be decreased to be held or flared. There is also a residual stream coming from the steam condensates which has an outlet temperature of 57 °C. These condensates come from the RH treatment and they are usually dusted.

For the secondary metallurgy the waste streams identified are the fumes, which leave at 250 °C and two streams of condensates coming from the RH station whose temperature is between 40-50 °C.

For the third stage of the steel shop, the continuous casting, the streams are the steam generated during the continuous casting cooling and the slabs.

Generally, the steel shop is a producer of steam and it sends the steam surplus to the general network of the plant. However, for some applications, i.e. central heating or degassing systems, steel shop consumes steam (about 10 kt/year) from the grid at lower pressures (15-18 bar).

Regarding the application of the heat pump within the steel shop, its use is limited since, as mentioned, the steel shop has an excess of steam and the steam needs higher pressures than the heat pump could provide.

3.1.2 Hot strip mill

The hot strip mill is a rolling mill of several stands of rolls that converts slabs from continuous casting into hot-rolled coils. This process allows regulating the force, temperature and time variables, and control the microstructure to achieve the desirable properties in the final product.

The streams produced at this part of the installation are shown in Figure 3-2. As shown, in the first step, the slabs are heated up to 1200 °C in walking beam furnaces. The flue gases leave the furnace at 800 °C and they are used to preheat the combustion air up to 400 °C. The outlet temperature of these gases after the air preheaters is between 400 °C to 450 °C, in a flow of 70000 Nm³/h.

The cooling water of the reheating furnace is in a closed circuit, where the water which leaves the furnace at 60 °C is cooled down to 55 °C. This water has been identified as a residual waste stream.

As can be seen in Figure 3-2, there is a steam consumption in the breaking down mill and in the finishing mill. Nevertheless, this consumption is lower than other stages of the process (2t/h), the consumption peaks occur after stops and there are no estimations of this steam monthly consumption.

The residual water from the breaking down mill, finishing mill and run table usually holds a big amount of residuals, like oil or mill scale, which goes to the water treatment plant. These conditions make it unfeasible to recover heat from these streams.

Figure 3-2. Hot strip mill main streams

A restriction to the integration of a heat pump is that even though the amount of gases from the reheating furnace is high, they are evacuated by natural draft. The insertion of some exchanger from the furnace may increase the pressure loss of the system, so forced vent (exhauster) may be needed if additional systems are introduced to compensate the pressure loss.

It must be also taken into consideration that the furnaces were installed on the current facilities 30 years ago and they do not reach a high efficiency level, so the installation of equipment to recover the waste heat is difficult and expensive.

3.1.3 Galvanizing lines

Even though there are two galvanizing lines within the Avilés plant, the characterization of the waste streams corresponds only to the Galvanizing line 2, since there is no recorded data from Galvanizing line 1. Therefore, the Figure 3-3 describes the main streams identified for Galvanizing line 2.

Figure 3-3. Galvanizing line 2 main streams

In this line, the degreasing section is the main steam consumer, using this steam to heat water or liquids to clean the strips, heat the air to dry the band and to control the thickness of the zinc coating. After degreasing there is a radiant tube furnace divided into two zones. The fumes are first gathered in a collector and then evacuated via a stack. These gases, whose flow reaches up to 20000 Nm³/h for the stack 1 are forced by extractor fans. This requires the dilution of the fumes in order to avoid fan damages, leaving the stacks with a temperature between 300 °C-350 °C. Recovering heat from the gases downstream the two zones of the reheating furnace is technically possible. However, together with the limitation of available room for the new facilities and the associated costs, the outlet gases temperature must be over 180 °C - 200 °C in order to avoid corrosive condensates, so the heat recovery would be limited.

The galvanizing line has some sources of quality water to generate steam with a heat pump. However, this water is at ambient conditions, needs to be heated and it is used for cleaning the

strip. Thus, the hot water after the cleaning process does not have enough quality to be used as heat source for the heat pump.

3.1.4 Continuous annealing line

In the continuous annealing line, the strips coming from the cold rolling are heated and then cooled in a controlled process in order to regenerate their internal structure. Figure 3-4 shows the main streams from this line.

Figure 3-4. Continuous annealing line main streams

In a first step, the strip is cleaned with water at a temperature between 70 °C-90 °C. This water stream has a potential interest to be used to feed the heat pump, but since it comes from a cleaning process, the water has a lot of residuals. There is also a steam stream to keep the temperature of the cleaning baths with a potential amount of hot condensates.

After drying, the strip is introduced in a reheating furnace, whose fumes are collected and blown by an extractor fan. The temperature of these fumes must be reduced by mixing them with air at 25 °C in order to avoid damaging the extractor fan. Finally, the mixed stream, with a flow of 30000 Nm³/h is expelled at a temperature between 200 °C-300 °C.

The rest of the process consists in some cooling stages using hot water and hot air. The temperature of the air after the cooling stages makes it unfit for being used as heat source for the heat pump.

3.1.5 Pickling line

The pickling line is the first step in the cold rolling, where the strip is cleaned from oxides. The strip is immersed into hydrochloric acid baths. Finally, the strip is cleaned with water and dried. Figure 3-5 shows the main streams from this line.

Figure 3-5. Pickling line main streams

The first heat streams in the pickling line are identified after the scale breaker, when the strip is introduced into the acid tanks to completely remove this scale. These tanks are filled with hydrochloric acid at a temperature around 90 °C. In order to increase the efficiency of the process, the temperature must be homogeneous around 70 °C-80 °C throughout all the tanks, which are covered with steam coils to achieve this homogeneity.

The acid solution is fed to these tanks by a closed circuit where a flow of 6.5 m³/h of acid is heated up to 90 °C before being introduced into the acid tanks. The dirty acid after the scale removal returns to a regeneration plant, where it is cleaned, heated and reintroduced into the circuit. Part of the acid is vaporized during the process, so new and old acid are mixed within the regeneration plant.

From the regeneration plant, a flow of 8000-9000 Nm³/h of fumes at a temperature between 60 °C and 80 °C is expelled.

The regeneration plant operates continuously but it is stopped for some hours every two weeks and for some days in winter and summer. This leads to a decrease of the temperature of the acid solution which leaves the regeneration plant. Moreover, during the transport of the acid through the pipes, the temperature decreases, so a constant consumption of steam is needed to ensure the acid input temperature to the tanks.

The next steps include the cleaning and drying of the strip in three steps: cold cleaning, hot cleaning and drying. The hot cleaning consumes demineralized water which has been previously heated from around 18 °C to 85 °C. The water after cleaning the strip is further used to clean the acid vapors from the acid tanks. The drying step has also a steam consumption in order to heat the air used for drying the strip.

All the steam consumed within the pickling line generates a waste stream of condensates between 5-6 m³/h at a temperature of 80 °C, which could be potentially used as source for a heat pump. However, this stream has some disadvantages, like the presence of rests of hydrochloric acid, which must be addressed to enable its use.

3.2 TÜPRAS

As mentioned in D2.2, the selected waste heat stream for TÜPRAS demo-site is the AR coming out from the CDU and going into an intermediate storage tank before being delivered to other downstream processes. Part of the heat from this stream is first internally reused to preheat other streams of the unit, and then is directed to the cooling system to lower its temperature to the required level for the downstream processes. The cooling system consists of a combination of an air cooler and water coolers. The initial and final design temperature conditions of the AR, as well as the inlet temperatures of the cooling fluids and the outer temperature for the cooling water are shown in Figure 3-6.

Figure 3-6. Layout of present AR stream cooling system at Tüpras

From a heat balance of the water coolers, the amount of heat that can be removed by them is estimated. This estimation yields that about 40% of the available heat of the AR stream is removed by the water coolers, the remaining 60% being removed by the air coolers.

Then, an estimation of the parameters of the present coolers has been obtained by the use of HEX sizing tools [3], along with typical values for several parameters such as fan efficiencies [4] and fouling factors [5], and stream data provided by TÜPRAS. To calculate the effectiveness-NTU relationships for the HEXs, the following assumptions have been made:

- Air cooler is of the finned tube type, e-NTU relations for crossflow HEX with air mixed and AR unmixed
- Water coolers are of double pipe type, e-NTU relations for counterflow HEX

Figure 3-7 shows the results of those calculations adapted to the streams characteristics of the AR cooling system, where the design points of the existing HEXs are indicated. From those results it can be concluded that:

- The air cooler is already optimized in terms of trade-off between CAPEX and OPEX, since increasing either of them (bigger HEX or higher air flowrate) and thus obtaining higher NTU values, will result in reduced effectiveness increase.
- Quite small water coolers are used (low NTU value). This can be justified by the low heat duty required from them under nominal operating conditions, due to most of the cooling requirement being handled by the air cooler upstream, as it has been pointed before. However, if additional heat duty is required from them (e.g. in case AR flowrates higher than nominal arise), there is still floor to increase NTU value by U improvement due to higher film coefficient on the AR side.

Figure 3-7. HEX parameters of present AR cooling system

The above reference parameters will later be compared with the waste heat recovery solution considered in the next chapter.

3.3 GRECIAN MAGNESITE

The selected waste heat stream (300 °C, 1 bar) is currently cooled down to comply with the specifications of downstream processes. The flue gases are cooled down to 170 °C using water injection. However, this heat loss can be used by an ORC installation to produce electricity. The

input temperature is quite high (300 °C) and the flue gases could be further cooled down to at least 150 °C, since 170 °C is the maximum acceptable temperature for downstream processes.

The heat source stream mass flow is 16 kg/s and its composition is presented in Table 3-1. The heat should be recovered before the Desulfurisation unit and gas conditioning tower.

Table 3-1. Heat source stream composition

Stream composition	O ₂	CO ₂	H ₂ O	SO ₂	N ₂
mole fraction (%)	0.1001	0.1732	0.0189	0.0017	0.7061

The waste heat derived from the temperature drop from 300 °C to 170 °C is estimated at 2182.8 kW_{th}.

3.4 UPM

In order to assess the waste-heat recovery potential, the analysis of energy and material flows has been carried out at factory level for the paper mill located in Plattling. Aiming at simplifying the visualization, five main units have been considered

- Energy and water supply**, including
 - gas supply to operate the combined heat and power (CHP) plant, generating 100% of the heat demand and around 70% of the electricity demand, as well as the back-up boiler
 - power supply from the grid to meet the demand not covered by the CHP plant
 - two compressors, producing compressed air for the production units
 - water supply from the Isar river and the freshwater treatment plant, to remove particulate contaminants and reduce the water hardness
- Production unit 1**, including chemical pulp preparation, mechanical pulp processing (grinders) and one paper machine, producing uncoated supercalendered (SC) paper
- Production unit 2**, including chemical pulp preparation, grinders, two paper machines and coating machines, where light-weight coated (LWC) paper is produced. Since July 2019 only one paper machine is in operation, as the paper machine 10 has been shut down.
- Recycling facility**, where recycled paper is de-inked and converted into fibre to be then used in the second production unit
- Waste-water and sludge treatment**, where waste-water is collected and treated before being discharged to the river and sludge is processed before disposal

Buildings and other services not related to the production have been neglected.

For electricity, gas and heat streams, demand values on monthly basis were collected and aggregated according to the assumed simplifications mentioned above. In order to calculate the embedded energy content in freshwater, waste-water and sludge, flow rate and temperature values were collected for each stream. The assumptions made for the calculations are specified in Table 3-2.

Table 3-2: Specifications of material streams to calculate embedded energy content

Stream	Parameter	Value
Water	Heat capacity	4,19 kJ/(kg*K)
	Density	1000 kg/m ³
Sludge (5% dry matter)	Calorific value	0,5 MJ/kg _{dry_matter}
	Density	1000 kg/m ³
Sludge (28% dry matter)	Calorific value	3 MJ/kg _{dry_matter}
	Density	1150 kg/m ³

As a result of the analysis it has been observed that the paper machines and the grinders are the biggest energy consumers, as regards both the heat and the electricity demand (see Figure 3-8).

As concerns the boundary conditions defined jointly with UPM in the first phase of the project, i.e. the waste-water and sludge treatment, the main outcome of the analysis is the possibility to valorize waste-water streams from the production. Waste-water from the grinding process in the first production unit has indeed a temperature of 80 °C. Waste-heat from paper machines has also high recovery potential. The options considered to recover those streams are described in detail in the following chapter.

Figure 3-8: Sankey diagram - Energy flows at the UPM demo-site

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820771. Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

4 WASTE HEAT RECOVERY ANALYSIS

For each of the combinations of waste heat stream and recovery technology selected in each demo-site, the performance of the recovery integration has been assessed and the potential benefits and drawbacks have been identified and if possible quantified.

4.1 Pinch analysis in AMIII

4.1.1 Pickling Line basis pinch analysis

According to the analysis of the different waste streams available in the different processes of AMIII, the pickling line, located within the Avilés facilities, has been identified as an optimal candidate to integrate the heat pump, since it currently has a consumption of external steam which can potentially be replaced by the steam produced by the heat pump, and it has a source of water with sufficient quality to be used as feed water for the heat pump. The pickling line has also some waste streams at different temperatures which can potentially become heat sources.

In a first step, no real constraints, like available space or distance between streams have been introduced in the analysis. This allows identifying the location of the heat exchangers where the maximum waste energy benefit would be obtained. However, there are some technical and economic issues which limit the utilization of the streams.

Table 4-1 summarizes the different streams characterized for the pickling line. These streams are also highlighted in Figure 3-5, in order to identify their location within the process:

Table 4-1: Energy streams and temperatures of the pickling line

Stream	T _{in}	T _{out}
1. Acid baths (energy to keep temperature almost constant)	89 °C	90 °C
2. Acid transport	70 °C	90 °C
3. Fumes from the regeneration plant	60-80 °C	25 °C
4. Condensates from the steam streams	80 °C	25 °C
5. Air for drying	25 °C	85 °C
6. Demineralized water	18 °C	85 °C

For this base analysis, most of the streams have been characterized onsite in Avilés. However, in some cases the streams are waste products without any further interest, so their values of temperature or flows are not measured. In the case of streams whose energy values could not be measured, they have been calculated using the data gathered in [6].

The resulting streams from the analysis of the pickling line are collected in Figure 4-1. According to the pinch methodology, the so-called "cold streams" are those that require an increase in temperature to be used, like the acid of the baths, the air for drying and the water used in the hot cleaning; while the hot streams are the ones that need cooling. For the pickling line case, those hot streams correspond to the fumes from the regenerator and the condensates from the steam of the already installed heat exchangers. These streams come from the process and they are wasted, so it is important to mention that there are no needs of external cooling within the

pickling line. All the energy which can be recovered from these streams will help to optimize the efficiency of the line.

Figure 4-1 Streams identified in the pickling line in Avilés

The pinch methodology requires the definition of a minimum difference of temperatures between two streams to allow the heat exchange. For this analysis, a minimum heat exchange temperature (ΔT_{\min}) of 20 °C has been chosen.

The composite curves, showed in Figure 4-2, are the graphic representation of the energy of the cold and hot streams versus the temperature, with the minimum approach of 20 °C between them. From the analysis of the curves, it can be seen how the $\Delta T_{\min}=20$ °C, implies the cold streams can start to exchange energy at 18 °C while the hot streams at 38°C, leading to a pinch temperature of 28 °C. The grey area between the curves is the amount of heat that can be effectively exchanged between the processes of the pickling line.

Since the energy needs from the cold streams are high, the energy available from the hot streams does not cover the whole heating, so there would be a need of external utilities (steam) to increase the temperature of the cold streams.

Figure 4-2 Hot and Cold composite curves

Nevertheless, there is some potential heat recovery from the waste streams, 3 and 4, which can be optimally used to increase the temperature of the stream 6, which is the closest streams to the pinch.

A first base analysis has been developed to assess the potential heat recovery within the current streams available in the pickling line by defining the heat exchangers required for this heat recovery. Figure 4-3 shows the scheme of the initial configuration of the pickling line streams. In this initial step, it can be shown that all the heating requirements are provided by external steam.

Figure 4-3. Pickling line initial

Following the pinch methodology, the new heat exchanger network must start at the temperatures closest to the pinch, which implies that in our case, the cold streams start to receive heat from the hot streams at 18 °C.

The stream 6 (demineralized water), which is the stream at 18°C, needs an amount of energy high enough to exhaust the energy available in the streams 4 and 5, so it has been divided in two sub-streams.

The stream 6a exchanges heat with the stream 4, so that the temperature of the stream 4 is decreased down to 38 °C, which is the pinch upper limit (the hot streams cannot exchange heat below it). The stream 6a leaves the heat exchanger 1 at 60 °C. After this exchange, the stream 4 heat is exhausted.

The stream 6b exchanges energy with the stream 3, which is also exhausted. Whether the stream 6a at 60 °C and the current 6b at 34.71 °C are mixed (with a final temperature of 44.8 °C) or treated individually, they would need additional energy to be heated up to the process temperature of 85 °C.

Figure 4-4 shows the basic heat exchanger network derived from the pinch analysis of the pickling line, as it has been explained.

Figure 4-4 Heat exchangers network obtained from the pinch analysis of the pickling line

After the potential use of the waste streams, there is a need of external energy to increase the temperature of the rest of the cold streams, which is currently covered with external steam heat exchangers. However, since the hot streams are wasted, there is no need of additional external cooling of these streams.

The use of heat exchangers 1 and 2 is an optimal solution obtained from the pinch analysis which would bring a decrease of 22 % in the total pickling line steam consumption. However, there are some constraints to be evaluated, especially, the economic constraints, since there are some investments to be performed, in addition to the cost of the heat exchangers, like for example the cost of the piping or pumping, which can be high due to the big distances to cover within the pickling line (around 500m. long) or the room required for the heat pump.

Thus, even though the use of the waste streams to reduce energy consumption is an optimal utilization of the resources, the implementation of this solution would involve a detailed financial analysis, according to the constrains mentioned.

4.1.2 High temperature heat pump integration

4.1.2.1 Introduction

Heat pumps can be integrated both in the cooling system and to recover the heat of the process. The representation of the heating and cooling requirements of the process taking into account the temperature levels (GCC curve) allows to identify the most adequate utilities to provide these requirements. Figure 4-5 presents the GCC curve for the pickling line. The optimal location of the heat pump should be through the pinch line in order to carry the heat from below the pinch, where there is a need of cooling, to above the pinch where there is a need of heat, decreasing simultaneously the need for heating and cooling services.

Figure 4-5 GCC curve

However, in the specific case of the pickling line, there is no need of cooling below the pinch, since the streams are residual, and the heat pump needs a temperature higher than the pinch temperature, so the integration of the heat pump needs to be performed over the pinch temperature.

The high temperature heat pump to be installed within the pickling line of AMIII requires a temperature of the heat source of typically 60-90 °C to produce steam at 152 °C. Figure 4-6 shows the typical temperature ranges of the high temperature heat pumps for some industry sectors (*source: AIT*).

Figure 4-6 Typical temperature ranges for the heat pump within the scope of Bamboo project. (Source: Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH)

The high temperature heat pump also requires a source of hot water, at around 102 °C, with enough quality to be used to generate the steam which will be used in the process. The pickling line has a source of demineralized water at a mean temperature of 18 °C, which can be used as feed water for the heat pump. To introduce this water in the analysis pinch, an additional cold stream (stream 7) has been added to the initial pinch analysis. This stream will require an amount of energy to be heated up to 102 °C, which are the working conditions for the heat pump

4.1.2.2 Pinch analysis with integrated heat pump

The energy needed to heat the feed water (stream 7) until its working temperature can be obtained from the own heat pump condensates or from any other source (other stream, external steam, heat pump steam...).

For this analysis, two different cases are evaluated for the heat pump integration, depending whether the steam condensates generated by the heat pump are mixed with the demineralized water stream (condensates act as heat source for stream 7) or added to the rest of condensates stream (energy to heat the feed water comes from the steam generated by the heat pump).

In the case A, the condensates are not mixed (e.g. can be introduced in the rest of the steam condensates stream, point 4 of Figure 3-5) and the stream 7 has an inlet temperature of 18°C, because it is the temperature of the demineralized water. For the case B, the condensates are mixed, the mixture composed by condensates from the heat pump and feed water would have a temperature of 85.7 °C, taking into account that the 88 % of the condensates can be recovered at 95 °C [7].

Figure 4-7 presents the streams updated for the case of the heat pump integration, in which the stream 7 has been included, starting in 18 °C or in 85.7 °C depending on the condensates route.

Figure 4-7 Streams in the pickling line for the heat pump integration

The heat pump heating needs can be covered by the stream 4 at 80 °C. The heat pump operating conditions will lead the stream 4 to decrease its temperature to 75 °C, so the final temperature availability of the stream 4 is from 75 °C to 25 °C.

As shown in Figure 4-8, the integration of the heat pump requires that part of the steam generated by the heat pump is used to preheat the feed water up to the operation temperature (102 °C). Depending on the condensates' recovery, the amount of energy needed to heat the stream 7 will be different, since the initial temperature will be 18 °C if condensates are not mixed, or 85.7 °C if the condensates are mixed with this feed water.

The rest of the steam generated by the heat pump can be used to increase the temperature of the stream 2, which corresponds to the acid stream used in the baths, reaching a temperature of 75.7 °C when the heat pump condensates are not used to feed the heat pump (case A) or 77.2 °C if the condensates of the heat pump are mixed with the feed water (case B). These temperatures have been calculated considering the energy available in the stream 4 is the same for those cases and the efficiency of a high temperature heat pump with the technical characteristics presented in [8].

The amount of global pickling line condensates (stream 4) varies between 5 t/h and 6 t/h, and we assume it to be 5.5 t/h for this analysis. Thus, even though the part of the condensates from the heat pump are re-circulated, and consequently removed from the main condensates stream (stream 4), the energy within this stream is not altered.

Figure 4-8 Heat exchangers network for the case of heat pump integration

Figure 4-9 shows the virtual configuration of the integrated heat pump in the pickling line. The figure refers only to the heat pump integration, so the heat exchangers 1 and 2 calculated from the basis pinch analysis are not showed. These heat exchangers would help to improve the global efficiency of the line, but they would not modify the operation mode of the heat pump.

As shown, the steam generated by the heat pump would require a new heat exchanger coupled to the acid line coming from the regeneration plant. In this case, the heat exchanger has been placed before the existing heat exchanger, whose steam consumption would be reduced a 28.5 % in the case A and a 36 % in the case B.

Another new heat exchanger is needed to heat the demineralized water from 18 °C (case A) or 85.7°C (case B) to 102 °C which will be connected to the original water line or to a new vessel depending on where the mixture of condensates and feed water would be performed.

Figure 4-9 Diagram of the pickling line with the heat pump integration

Case A. Adding condensates to the main condensates stream

Case B. Mixing condensates and demineralized water

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 820771. Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein

Table 4-2 Summary of the results from the different analysis

Option	Steam consumption	N° Heat exchangers	Q recovered vs Q wasted
Base case (as is, w/o integration)	100 %	0	0
Theoretical pinch analysis (w/o heat pump)	78.1 %	2	75.3 %
Case A. Heat pump integration	97.1 %	2 (HP)	9.8 %
Case B. Heat pump integration	96.4 %	2 (HP)	12.4 %
Case A + heat recovery	77.3 %	2 (HP) +2	77.8 %
Case B + heat recovery	76.5 %	2 (HP) +2	80.4 %

The different cases covered in this analysis are summarized in Table 4-2. The implementation of the two heat exchangers deduced from the pinch analysis would suppose a final steam consumption in the pickling line of the 78.1 % of the current consumption.

The impact of the BAMBOO heat pump would drop the consumption to the 97.1 % or 96.4 %, considering that in this case the real constraints have been used to dimension it. The potential decrease with this technology is really high when the conditions are appropriate.

Finally, from an energetic and environmental point of view, the implementation of a heat pump whose condensates are to be used as feed water, combined with the two heat exchangers will suppose a reduction of the 23.5 % in the total steam consumption, but a deep economic analysis must be performed taking into consideration all the real restrictions.

4.1.2.3 Heat pump conditions analysis

The integration of the heat pump has been carried out assuming some specific conditions, but in the real processes of the pickling line there is some variability in the streams which can modify the operation point of the heat pump and thus, the amount of steam generated. For the sake of completeness, a sensitivity analysis on the most influential parameters has been performed.

One parameter which can fluctuate is the amount of condensates depending on the steam used in the process. The typical values are between 5 t/h and 6 t/h. This situation can lead to a variability in the power generated by the heat pump if the rest of the variables are fixed. For the analysis performed in this document, a fixed amount of 5.5 t/h was assumed. Figure 4-10 shows the variation in the temperature of the stream 2 after the heat pump heat exchange, where differences of about 1.5 °C are expected depending on the amount of condensates.

Figure 4-10 Temperature of the stream 2 after exchange heat with the heat pump vs amount of condensates from the process

On the other hand, the working conditions of the heat pump are strongly related to the heat source and heat sink temperatures, being able to triple its COP when increasing the temperature of the source for the same temperature of the sink [8]. For the analysis performed in this document, a temperature of 80 °C of the heat source was assumed.

For the pickling line, a potential increase in the temperature from 80 °C to 100 °C for a medium flow of condensates (5.5 m³/h) would lead to a virtual increase on the temperature of the stream 2 from 77.2 °C to 85 °C, as it can be seen on Figure 4-11. Although it is difficult to implement in the industrial case, this would lead to an optimal use of the heat pump technology.

Figure 4-11 Temperature of the stream 2 after exchange heat with the heat pump vs temperature of condensates from the process

4.1.3 Conclusions

During this task, a pinch analysis of the AMIII pickling line has been performed in a theoretical way, skipping some real constraints, e.g. the costs and losses of a very long piping between stages or the room available for the heat pump installation.

This theoretical integration of the heat pump within the pickling line leads to a reduction in the total line steam consumption of 2.9 % or 3.6 %, depending on how the heat pump condensates are treated, which implies a direct reduction in natural gas consumption and CO₂ emissions.

For the real application, it should be taken into account that the operation conditions of the industrial case of the pickling line are fixed and thus, the operation points bounded. Nevertheless, the laboratory trials planned on the scope of WP4 of BAMBOO project will help to confirm the potential values of the high temperature heat pump at different conditions and thus, to know the potential of replication outside the BAMBOO project.

From the economical point of view, the flexibility tool which will be developed during WP6 of BAMBOO will help AMIII to decide the optimum operational conditions according to the different scenarios and depending upon external factors like electricity and steam prices and working conditions.

Finally, the final implementation in the AMIII demo site during WP8 will demonstrate the potential of waste heat recovery in the steel sector, which is one of the main objectives targeted for BAMBOO project.

4.2 TÜPRAS

The following sections summarize the main steps and conclusions obtained from the waste heat to ORC analysis for Tüpras demo-site. As most of the information used for and obtained from this analysis is confidential, only global or percentage figures are reported in this public document (however, detailed calculation data are available for the involved partners).

4.2.1 ORC and AR waste heat stream integration

As a first step towards the integration of the ORC system to recover the waste heat of the AR stream, the tie in connection point has been defined both for the evaporator and for the condenser at the CDU process. Figure 4-12 shows the chosen layout for those connection points along with the main components of the ORC. The ORC is connected upstream of the present cooling system with the possibility of taking only the required amount of heat for driving the evaporation process. In this way, any fluctuations on the AR stream (both flow rate and temperature) not being handled by the ORC system, can be addressed by the present cooling system, and the resulting outlet temperature of the AR stream remains the same as today.

Figure 4-12. Layout for ORC integration at Tüpras

Starting from the above layout, heat balances for the evaporator and condenser have been calculated in order to define the ORC operational parameters (i.e. condensing and evaporating temperatures and working fluid mass flowrate). ORC main parameters have been previously defined by TURBODEN (D3.1 *Preliminary Design Of The ORC Solution*), and those reference values have been used for these calculations.

The results from those heat balances show that slightly above half of the AR cooling energy is used for evaporating the working fluid, while the rest is mainly used for the liquid preheating (with just a small percentage used for gas superheating). Thus, it makes sense to separate the working fluid heating HEX in 2 separate exchangers (preheater and evaporator), so as to accommodate each design to the specific purpose.

On the contrary, regarding condensing of the working fluid, the calculations show that above 90% of the cooling water energy is used for the condensation process and thus a single HEX is considered for this purpose. It is worth noting that for this condenser, a flowrate of water higher than the one required for the present water coolers is required, which besides the need of increased capacity of the plant cooling water system, could require a higher pumping power depending on the HEX pressure losses. However, this drawback has to be balanced against the benefit of not operating the air coolers, and thus saving the electric consumption of the fans (besides the straightforward benefit of the ORC electricity production).

Finally, the inclusion of a regenerator means an additional 10% recovery of the heat from the AR vs. the scenario with no such HEX, and thus, its use is justified.

On the above balances, more than 2 MW average electrical power is foreseen to be produced by the ORC system by using the AR cooling energy.

4.2.2 Sizing of ORC system HEX

Based on the available data for AR stream parameters (flow and temperature data for a 2-year interval, as well as available cooling water's flow and temperature) in the context of WP3 TURBODEN has selected some ORC features (such as working fluid, evaporation and condensation temperatures, etc.). By using those values as fixed parameters and applying heat balances to the different components and the whole thermodynamic cycle, the rest of parameters for the ORC/AR cooling integration have been estimated. Again, as in the case of the existing AR cooling system in the previous chapter, HEX sizing tools have been used to estimate the required parameter for them. In this case, the following assumptions have been made for the ORC system HEXs:

- Condenser, evaporator and regenerator calculated using crossflow e-NTU relations
- Preheater calculated using parallel counterflow e-NTU relations, comparing one and two shell passes.

Figure 4-13 shows the results of those calculations adapted to the ORC/AR cooling integrated streams, where the design points estimated for HEXs are indicated. From those results it can be concluded that:

- Condenser and evaporator design point is close to the end of the approximate linear range of the e-NTU curve. Considering that the ORC electrical output is strongly related with the latent heat transfer at those both exchangers, any improvement in their effectiveness will translate into an increased power generation capacity due to allowing higher evaporating and lower condensing temperatures. But starting from the design points of the figures, any further increase of the size (NTU) of those exchangers will result in proportionally lower effectiveness increments. Thus, an increase in the cost of those HEX will not translate into the same proportionality to the power output and thus no benefit is foreseen from this.
- Preheater design point and e-NTU relations show that a multipass option is required for the selected configuration, as the single pass option is not able to achieve the required effectiveness independently of the HEX size. Alternatively, increasing the number of passes beyond a 2-pass configuration brings no additional benefit. Once this 2-pass configuration is chosen, the design point in the curve is such that further increase of the size is no worth due to effectiveness increases not being attractive enough.
- Finally, the design point of the regenerator is quite beyond the linear range of the e-NTU curve. Although this could seem a drawback in terms of system cost, it should be pointed that the benefits from a more effective regenerator are translated into the power output of the ORC (and thus shorten payback time), while its relative cost compared to that of the whole ORC system may not be that high. This is typical for example in gas turbine regenerators [9].

Figure 4-13. HEX parameters for the ORC/AR cooling integration

As a summary of the above results it can be concluded that the design point of the HEXs of an ORC cycle for cooling Izmir refinery's AR stream have been selected following good engineering practice, with a trade-off between system cost and benefit from on-site electricity generation.

4.2.3 Conclusions

The results of the calculations done for the integration of an ORC system in the AR cooling process of the CDU at Izmir refinery show that no significant penalty is added to the existing cooling system: AR and cooling water pumping powers remain the same as in the present cooling process. Moreover, beside the straightforward benefit of in-situ electricity generation by the ORC in the order of 2 MW average power, an additional electricity saving arises due to the air coolers not being required for AR cooling, and thus the cooling fans can be stopped (or at least operated at a lower power) resulting in average power savings close to 100 kW.

The calculations above have been based on design values. However, AR stream is variable due to refinery fuel production variability. The ORC design can handle those fluctuations to a certain limit, and thus, the present cooling system will be operating in parallel to assume the cooling capacity not addressed by the ORC.

4.3 GRECIAN MAGNESITE

4.3.1 Thermodynamic Simulations

The potential of heat recovery from a waste stream of known characteristics, via an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC), has been investigated. The ORC scheme as well as the boundary conditions used for the simulations are presented in Figure 4-14 and in Table 4-3, respectively. The heat source stream at 300 °C entering the ORC heater (evaporator) is named as HS_{in} while the cooling medium that is used in the condenser is water (CW_{in} , 15 °C). In this initial -proof of concept- analysis, the inclusion of an intermediate heat exchanger where a thermal oil is used to transfer the heat from the hot flue gas to the ORC working medium is not considered. It should be underlined that probably this intermediate step will be needed in reality.

Figure 4-14. Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) scheme

Table 4-3. Boundary conditions used for simulations

Heater Pinch point	35 °C
Recuperator Pinch point	20 °C
Condenser pinch point	10 °C
Turbine isentropic efficiency, $\eta_{is,turb}$	0.75
Pump isentropic efficiency, $\eta_{is,pump}$	0.80
Turbine mechanical efficiency, $\eta_{m,turb}$	0.98
Generators mechanical efficiency, $\eta_{m,gen}$	0.98

An important factor related to the ORC efficiency is the selection of the appropriate working fluid. Some conventional working fluids were selected as well as some mixtures of them obtained from relative studies [10], [11]. The ORC efficiency in each case is defined as:

$$\text{ORC Efficiency: } \eta = \frac{Pel(TURB) - Pel(PUMP)}{Waste\ heat\ (2182.8\ kW)}$$

where Pel (TURB) is the Turbine electrical production, Pel (PUMP) the Pump electrical consumption and Waste heat the available heat load obtained from the waste heat stream.

Table 4-4 shows the main results for the simulations performed. Taking into consideration the results obtained from the simulations, it can be observed that the ORC efficiency is around **20%**. Another fact is that the ORC efficiency is a multivariable parameter (working fluid, mixture/non mixture, subcritical/supercritical operation, heat exchangers pinch points) that under optimization conditions can overpass the 20% (for example the supercritical case in Table 4-4).

Table 4-4. ORC simulation results

		1	2	3	4	5	6	HSin	HSout	CWin	CWout
BUTANE/CYCLOPENTANE (50/50 mole fraction)	p (bar)	35.4	35.4	35.4	2.3	2.3	2.3	1	1	1	1
	T (C)	41.9	142.2	264.9	192.3	61.9	40	300	170	15	30
	mass flow (kg/s)	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2	16	16	25.2	25.2
	Pel (TURB) kW		Pel (PUMP) kW	ORC Efficiency η							
	487.96	30.29	0.2096								
BUTANE	p(bar)	33.6	33.6	33.6	3.8	3.8	3.8	1	1	1	1
	T (C)	42.3	141.6	265.1	207.9	62.3	40.2	300	170	15	30
	mass flow (kg/s)	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4	4.4	16	16	25.5	25.5
	Pel (TURB) kW		Pel (PUMP) kW	ORC Efficiency η							
	470.51	35.68	0.1992								
BUTANE/PROPANE (50/50 mole fraction)	p(bar)	33.8	33.8	33.8	8.2	8.2	8.2	1	1	1	1
	T (C)	41.1	116.4	264.9	222.5	61.1	38.6	300	170	15	30
	mass flow (kg/s)	4.8	4.8	4.8	4.8	4.8	4.8	16	16	26.7	26.7
	Pel (TURB) kW		Pel (PUMP) kW	ORC Efficiency η							
	388.53	35.93	0.1615								
BUTANE/CYCLOPENTANE (60/40 mole fraction)*	p(bar)	51.2	51.2	51.2	2.6	2.6	2.6	1	1	1	1
	T (C)	43.1	132.9	264.9	178.9	63.3	40.2	300	170	15	30
	mass flow (kg/s)	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2	16	16	25.1	25.1
	Pel (TURB) kW		Pel (PUMP) kW	ORC Efficiency η							
	511.24	30.82	0.2200								

*The last case refers to a supercritical ORC, meaning that the pressure of the working fluid in position 3 is higher than the critical pressure of the mixture

For a preliminary techno-economic assessment, it was chosen the first subcritical case of Table 4-4 (50-50 butane/cyclopentane) with an ORC efficiency equal to 20.96%. This can be a realistic cycle efficiency for commercially state of the art ORC units [12]. A techno-economic analysis has been performed for the first subcritical case in Table 4-4 (50-50 butane/cyclopentane) to assess

the payback period of the investment required to implement a waste heat recovery with the above estimated technical performance. Table 4-5 shows the main parameters of this techno-economic analysis, while Table 4-6 shows the impact on the electricity consumption of GM site for such a recovery investment.

Table 4-5. Techno-economic assessment

ORC Electrical capacity	450.80 kW _{el}
Estimated ORC specific capital cost ²	2000 €/kW _e
Estimated electricity cost based on GM bills	0.08 €/kWh
CAPEX	901610 €
Operating & Maintenance cost (5% CAPEX)	45080.5 €/year
Annual ORC Electricity production	3786762 kWh/year
Annual ORC Financial contribution	302941 €/year
Expected payback period	3.5 years

Table 4-6. GM site information

Annual electrical demand for the GM Kilns operation	8200000 kWh/year
Percentage of self-consumption coverage*	46%
Kiln operating time	96%

*all electricity produced by the ORC will be used for self-consumptions

4.3.2 Conclusions

The conclusions drawn from this techno-economic analysis are quite promising. For an ORC operation with a non-optimized heat recovery configuration, the percentage of self-consumption coverage is remarkable while the expected payback period is definitely within an acceptable range of 2-4 years. This can be even lower if the flue gases are further cooled down (e.g. at 150 °C) or an optimized cost-effective ORC cycle is selected. This first analysis reveals that the potential waste heat recovery with an ORC unit could be a promising and a profitable solution. Of course, a more detailed analysis, containing implementation feasibility and optimization of the operating conditions is needed that will lead to safer and more precise conclusions.

² <http://www.tasio-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/D8.4-TASIO-Adaptability-and-replicability-of-the-developed-technology.pdf>

4.4 UPM

In the assessment of the waste-heat recovery potential, the waste-water stream from the grinding machine PGW of the first production unit has been identified to have the highest valorization potential.

Three different scenarios for the recovery of the identified waste heat streams are currently being evaluated: scenario 1 and 2 consider the installation of waste-water heat exchangers and heat pumps with different inlet temperatures. The electricity required to operate the heat pumps will be supplied either by the grid or by the CHP plant. The third scenario consists in the installation of a steam heat exchanger, without valorizing waste-water streams.

4.4.1 Scenario 1

In order to recover the selected waste heat stream, the installation of two waste-water heat exchangers and two high temperature heat pumps (HTHP) is planned. The waste-water heat exchanger will be placed within the first production unit, close to the grinding machine. The heat pumps will instead be built near to the sludge drying system, within the waste-water and sludge treatment plant.

Figure 4-15: Heat supply scheme for the sludge drying facility - Scenario 1

Figure 4-15 shows the planned heat supply scheme for the sludge drying facility. In the presented configuration, the waste-water stream from the grinding process PGW, with a temperature of 80°C and a flow rate of 158 m³/h is conveyed to the heat exchanger, where the cooling medium (cold water) flowing in the pipes is heated to 66°C using the thermal energy from the waste-water inflow.

The transfer of the heated medium from the production unit to the waste-water treatment plant, where the heat pump will be located, would yield a temperature-loss of 1°C. The heat source of

the heat pump has thus a temperature of 65°C and is cooled down to 55°C and transferred back to the waste-water heat exchanger. The heat sink of the heat pump, with a temperature of 75°C and a flow rate of 87 m³/h, is heated-up to 90°C, supplying the sludge-dryer with thermal energy. The waste-water stream is returned into the waste-water system at a temperature of 71,9°C. Specifications of the heat pump are given in Table 4-7.

Table 4-7: Boundary conditions for the heat pump - Scenario 1

Parameter	Value
Number of HTHP	2
Electrical power demand of each HTHP	255 kW
Coefficient of performance of compressor	4
Warm water inlet	75°C
Warm water outlet	90°C
Cold water inlet	65°C
Cold water outlet	55°C

Through the heat pump, up to 2040 kW heating power can be generated to operate the drying system aiming at increasing the dry matter (DM) from 28% to 90%, with a consequent increment of the bio-sludge calorific value, decrease of its storage volume and disposal cost saving. Details related to sludge composition and the drier operation have been provided in D2.5 *Definition of specifications and data requirements for waste streams valorisation as fuels analysis*.

4.4.2 Scenario 2

The second scenario follows the same scheme as the first one, e.g. two heat exchangers and two heat pumps, with few changes in the operation of the heat pumps: the warm water inlet has a temperature of 80°C instead of 75°C and a higher flow rate (149 m³/h), as shown in Figure 4-16. The thermal energy provided to the drier would be slightly higher, 1671 kW compared to 1520 kW in the previous scenario, however the electrical power demand of each heat pump would increase by 5 kW. The boundary conditions of the heat pump are summarized in Table 4-8.

Figure 4-16: Heat supply scheme for the sludge drying facility - Scenario 2

Table 4-8: Boundary conditions for the heat pump - Scenario 2

Parameter	Value
Number of HTHP	2
Electrical power demand of each HTHP	260 kW
Coefficient of performance of compressor	4
Warm water inlet	80°C
Warm water outlet	90°C
Cold water inlet	65°C
Cold water outlet	55°C

4.4.3 Scenario 3

The third scenario consists in the installation of a steam heat exchanger to reach a higher temperature at the drier (see Figure 4-17). Through the use of saturated steam with an inlet temperature of 145°C to the heat exchanger, a maximal temperature of 95°C as heat source for the drier operation could be achieved (5°C higher than in the two previous scenarios). However,

this scenario would require the construction of a supply line to the dryer installation site, which would considerably increase the investments.

Figure 4-17: Heat supply scheme for the sludge drying facility - Scenario 3

4.4.4 Conclusions

The methodology used for the UPM use-case consisted in the characterization of energy flows and its visualization through a Sankey-diagram. All energy carriers have been considered, including gas, electricity, compressed air and heat as well as water, waste-water and sludge, since the main focus of the project lays on the waste-water treatment plant.

Based on the energy flows analysis, waste-heat flows have been assessed by means of their recovery potential, with the aim of valorising waste-heat streams to operate the sludge drying facility to be installed within the waste-water treatment plant. The most promising waste-heat stream is the waste-water of the grinding process connected to the first paper machine. Scenarios for the supply of the drying facility include the installation of heat exchangers and heat pumps. Two scenarios are based on the possibility to recover the identified waste-water flow with a combination of two waste-water heat exchangers and two heat pumps, operated with different boundary conditions in the two scenarios. The third scenario consists in the integration of a steam heat exchanger to achieve a higher temperature at the drier. All scenarios aim at an increased dry matter in bio-sludge, from around 30% up to 90%, in order to open up new possibility to valorise bio-sludge, which is currently a residual product, as described in D2.5.

5 REFERENCES

- [1] Kemp, I.C. (2006). Pinch Analysis and Process Integration: A User Guide on Process Integration for the Efficient Use of Energy, 2nd edition. Includes spreadsheet software. Butterworth-Heinemann. ISBN 0-7506-8260-4.
- [2] Pinch Analysis in the Oil&Gas Industries: http://www.oil-gasportal.com/pinch-analysis-in-the-oilgas-industries/#_ftn20
- [3] HEX calculator: <https://checalc.com/calc/AirExch.html>
- [4] https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com/fans-efficiency-power-consumption-d_197.html
- [5] https://www.engineeringpage.com/technology/thermal/fouling_factors.html
- [6] Reference Document on Best Available Techniques in the Ferrous Metals Processing Industry. Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control (IPPC). December 2001.
- [7] <https://beta.spiraxsarco.com/learn-about-steam/condensate-recovery/introduction-to-condensate-recovery>
- [8] HeatBooster. High-temperature heat pump brochure. <http://www.vikingheatengines.com/heatbooster>
- [9] Ramesh K. Shah, Dusan P. Sekulic, "Fundamentals of Heat Exchanger Design", 2003, p. 127
- [10] Braimakis K, Karellas S. Energetic optimization of regenerative Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) configurations. Energy Conversion and Management. 2018; 159:353-70.
- [11] Braimakis K, Preißinger M, Brüggemann D, Karellas S, Panopoulos K. Low grade waste heat recovery with subcritical and supercritical Organic Rankine Cycle based on natural refrigerants and their binary mixtures. Energy. 2015;88:80-92.
- [12] <https://www.turboden.com/applications/1053/waste-heat-recovery>.

ANNEX I. - GLOSSARY

General

HHP - High Temperature Heat Pump

ORC - Organic Rankine Cycle

CAPEX - Capital Expenditure

OPEX - Operational Expenditure

Steel use case

2M - Secondary Metallurgy

BOF - Basic Oxygen Furnace

BOFG - Basic Oxygen Furnace Gas

COG - Coke Oven Gas

LD Converter - Linz and Donawitz Converter

RH - Ruhrstahl Hereaus

Petrochemical use case

CDU - Crude Oil Distillation Unit

AR - Atmospheric Residue

HEX - Heat Exchanger

e - effectiveness of HEX

NTU - Number of Transfer Units

C_{min} - Minimum Heat Capacity of HEX streams

C_{max} - Maximum Heat Capacity of HEX streams

U - overall Heat Transfer coefficient of HEX

Pulp and Paper use case

PGW - Pressurized Groundwood

ANNEX II. - SUMMARY OF DEMO-SITE DESCRIPTIONS RELATED WITH WASTE HEAT RECOVERY

AMIII DEMO-SITE

AMIII Asturias plant is divided in two facilities, Gijón and Avilés, where different steel products are fabricated. Figure 5-1 presents a summary of the different process steps within these facilities.

Figure 5-1 Summary of the steel production processes at the ArcelorMittal Asturias plant

As shown, Gijón plant main facilities are the sintering, blast furnace, steel shop (LD converter and continuous casting) and three mills for the different products. At the Avilés plant, different coil products are manufactured, and several finishing lines are installed.

The different stages of the process in Avilés use a wide range of energy and fuel streams, and they also generate some residual streams which can potentially be used as energy sources. They are also intensive steam consumers at different conditions. Part of the steam is produced in the plant, and part of the steam is provided from external facilities. These reasons make Avilés plant optimal for energy flexibility, so the identification and characterization of the waste heat streams has been focused on Avilés.

TÜPRAS DEMO-SITE

Tüpras Izmir refinery, Figure 5-2, which started production in 1972 with an annual crude oil processing capacity of 3 million tons, is now registered as having an annual refining capacity of 11.9 million tons following significant capacity increases and unit modernizations carried out over the years.

The refinery's production of main marketable petroleum products -consisting of LPG, naphtha, gasoline, jet fuel, diesel, base oil, heating oil, fuel oil, bitumen, wax, extracts and other products-reached to 9.4 million tons in 2018. Izmir Refinery has a 400 thousand tons of capacity base oil production unit, the only one of its kind in Turkey. In 2018, the Izmir Refinery achieved sales of 10.1 million tons, of which 7.9 million tons were sold domestically.

Figure 5-2. Picture of Tüpras Izmir refinery

